

Biomedical Signal Archiving and Communication

Recommendations about the integration and implementation
of vital signs monitors in a future signal archive

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Preface

A mandatory part of the master phase of the study Biomedical Engineering is the internship. The aims of this practical training are to perform an assignment applying the principles and methods of Biomedical Engineering in a practical situation and to gain insight into the functioning of a professional organization. Since I like travelling I decided to look for an internship abroad and to look for an internship in Buenos Aires. Through a search in the scientific literature and the internet I found a four contact persons dispersed over universities and hospitals within Buenos Aires. Three out of four gave a positive reaction and I decided to go for the Hospital Italiano, because of the practical hospital environment. After a typical Argentine barbeque with the HIBA (Hospital Information Systems Society Buenos Aires) and talking to colleagues from other hospitals in Buenos Aires, I came to the conclusion that the Hospital Italiano is one of the most developed hospitals in Argentina, especially for it's hospital information system. Within the hospital I had the disposal of a computer at the Informatica Medica department. At the first place I want to thank my colleague Analia Baum for arranging the whole internship and the living in her house for three months. Besides that, I want to thank Fernando Plazzotta for arranging many practical things and information about Buenos Aires, Alejandro Figar for being my supervisor and providing the assignment and last but not least Jorge Garbino for being my daily supervisor, giving critical feedback and inviting me for dinner with his family. I had a great time in Buenos Aires and I hope this internship report has some surplus value for the hospital.

Abstract

A driver for medical device connectivity within the Hospital Italiano is the raising importance of legal issues and as a consequence a need of storing biomedical signal data. In order to do this the signals have to be transferred from the bedside equipment to a computer and several signals should be stored for a specific period of time in a suitable data standard. The whole system is called a Signal Archiving and Communication System (SACS) by the hospital. This report will provide a recommendation about the current possibilities for the Hospital Italiano to store the vital signs into an archive by making an extensive inventory of the suitable options. Storing vital signs brings some complications, due to differences in medical devices, data types and data formats. The most important data types are the electrocardiogram (ECG), the oxygen saturation of blood and the blood pressure values. These can be stored in common and less common data formats, like DICOM, CEN/ENV 1064, ASTM 1467, EDF, CEN-TC251/FEF, MFER.

A selection of monitors within the Hospital Italiano has been made and three solutions are presented. The first solution is using specialized suppliers in connecting several brands of bedside equipment in order to guarantee the signal storage, for example CapsuleTech. The second solution is the Philips IntelliVue Information center, because of the presence of new Philips MP40 monitors. Philips itself also offers an extensive package of networking tools to connect the Philips equipment in the hospital. The third solution is the in-house development in which the hospital should make a solution itself. They can make use of the already existing software like Ixcellence and get additional support from organizations like IHE. It is recommended to start using the licensed version of the Ixcellence software, use it during operations and in the meantime defining clear wishes and needs regarding the SACS from the hospital point of view. After that CapsuleTech or Sensitron can be suitable solutions.

Introduction

The biggest driver to medical device connectivity at the point of care is the Hospital Information System. Most of the hospitals nowadays use a HIS and in this situation, the natural need of connecting the hospital equipment to the HIS comes up, but it is also at this point that ignored issues of the past become fundamental. For instance if the medical device does not have any communication channel or removable media for transmitting or storing the examinations, but was selected only on the base of its functionality as stand-alone medical device, the integration in the healthcare information system will be not very seamless or very difficult. Most currently installed medical devices are several years old and lack connectivity capabilities beyond an RS232 serial port. Devices that are connected to a network, are mostly running on private networks and many of them are using outdated network infrastructure.

However, for providing optimal patient care it is required to have efficient access to all relevant information including the information from the monitors. Despite the advanced state of technology, most healthcare institutions cannot provide this until today. Besides the equipment problems, one of the largest obstacles for this implementation is the lack of communications standards in healthcare. Although standards such as DICOM and HL7 make interoperability possible, the absence of a coordinated implementation process allows the fragmented information architecture seen in most institutions today to persist [1].

However, many hospitals worldwide do have a Hospital Information System, but the extent in how it is used differs. Some progressive hospitals have the availability over a Picture Archiving and Information System (PACS), others don't. The Hospital Italiano in Buenos Aires, Argentina, developed their own Electronic Health Record which is operational since 1998 and is daily used by all the physicians in the hospital. For several reasons there is a raising need to store the biomedical signal data obtained from the bedside equipment or ventilation equipment during surgery. However, how this can be done, for which signals and which equipment is still unclear.

This report includes a recommendation about the integration and implementation of vital signs monitors in a future signal archive. In order to do this, chapter 1 will provide some general information about the Hospital Italiano followed by the current situation and the desired future situation regarding the signal storage in chapter 2. In this chapter, also a concise workflow analyses will be given. Chapter 3 provides general information about the storage of biomedical signals; which databases already exist, which data formats are used and what are the bottle necks with current databases. On the basis of this information, in chapter 4 a selection of monitors available in the Hospital Italiano will be made that are suitable for integration. Thereafter, in chapter 6, 7 and 8 the three solutions that are found will be presented in more detail. Chapter 9 continues on the requirements for the future archiving system and together with the future perspectives of equipment in healthcare in chapter 10 an extensive recommendation is provided in chapter 11.

1. Hospital Italiano

The Hospital Italiano de Buenos Aires (HIBA) is a non-profit, tertiary care, teaching and research hospital with more than 150 years of history. It has 650 inpatient beds with 130 beds in the intensive units care. The hospital receives 22.000 admissions and more than 1.200.000 outpatient visits annually, with an average of 15.000 surgical interventions. Every year the maternity department shelters 1500 birth and the hospital realizes approximately 120 transplantations for adults and pediatrics. For almost 30 years it also has its own Health Maintenance Organization (HMO), called the Plan de Salud, that takes care of a population of 150,000 patients. All these activities are distributed between 3500 employees that attend research and teach inside the institution, the Instituto Universitario. The hospital also works on the 'Campus Virtual', which is a proposal for learning at a distance which is used by the hospital for national-international courses and other activities for healthcare professionals.

Over 110 professionals work in the HIBA Information Systems Department distributing in five main areas: Developments, Technology, Epidemiology, Policies and Procedures and Medical Informatics. In this last one more than 30 health professionals are devoted to maintain the controlled vocabularies, test and deploy the Electronic Health Record from the medical viewpoint, develop rules for decision support and more. Since 2002, the hospital has had physicians in a residency program in medical informatics. It is the only 'medical informatics' post-graduate career for physicians in Argentina and they work as bridges between clinicians and the development team throughout the systems life cycle.

2. Current and future situation

A description of the current situation and the understanding of a desired future situation will eventually lead to the research question. Therefore an overview will be given of the current situation in the Hospital Italiano, existing of more detailed information about the Hospital Information System (HIS) and a short investigation of the available equipment. Thereafter the results of an interview with an anesthetist and the person responsible for the purchase of hospital equipment will be given in order to obtain more information about the preferred situation of the Hospital Italiano in the future. The research question will be formulated according to the wishes and needs of the hospital.

2.1 Hospital Information System

Since 1998 the Hospital Italiano has gradually implemented a full-scale Hospital Information System. This HIS is developed in-house, which means that no third parties were included in the development and only engineers working within the hospital took part in the development. Only where interfaces were needed, the hospital mandated the use of HL7 V2.x engines. The platforms in use are Oracle / J2EE / SUN for biomedical applications and AS400 or Oracle / J2EE / SUN for administrative applications. The first developed part of the HIS is the ambulatory Electronic Health Record (EHR). This EHR is web-based, patient centered and problem-oriented record. More than 1500 physicians, including general practitioners and specialists use it in their routine practice to take care of patients.

All components of the problem list are coded using ICPC-2-E, ICD-10 and Snomed CT. ICPC or International Classification of Primary Care is a classification method for primary care encounter. This allows healthcare professionals to classify three important elements of the healthcare encounter. These are the reason for encounter, diagnoses or problems and process of care [2]. ICPC-2-E refers to a revised electronic version which was released in 2000. The ICD-10, the International Statistical Classification of Diseases and Related Health Problems 10th revision is a coding of diseases and signs, symptoms, abnormal findings, complaints, social circumstances and external causes of injury as classified by the World Health Organization [3]. Snomed CT is the abbreviation of Systemized Nomenclature of Medicine and is a systematically organized computer processable collection of medical terminology. It provides a common language that enables a consistent way of capturing, sharing and aggregating health data across specialties and sites of care [4]. In the Hospital Italiano, a centralized coding department uses the free-text physician input to encode problems. The coders have already coded more than one million problems, assisted in this process by a text-matching algorithm that automatically codes more than 70% of the problems.

The other parts of the HIS consist of an emergency information system, an inpatient discharge summary, inpatient tracking systems, homecare tracking systems, scheduling systems, ADT (admission, discharge, transfer), management and reporting systems for ancillary services (imaging diagnostic, path lab, cardiology, nuclear medicine, clinical laboratory), clinical data repository, clinical event monitor, and administrative systems (Human resources, Inventory, Accounts, Pharmacy).

2.1.1 Picture Archiving and Communication System

The next step in the development of the Hospital Information System is the extension with a PACS system. This Picture Archiving and Communication System should provide a single point of access for images and their associated data and it should interface with the current HIS. In 2008 the Hospital Italiano will start a PACS-pilot project in cooperation with the University of Barcelona to store the X-Rays in a digital format.

2.2 Data exchange at OR

Besides the in-house development of the Hospital Information System and the upcoming PACS-pilot, anesthesiologist Mr. Figar is also coping with the in-house development of a system that is able to store the signals from the Philips IntelliVue MP40 monitor in the operating room [5]. The MP40 monitor itself is only able to store 30 seconds of vital signs data which can be viewed in Microsoft Access or Excel. Besides that 48 or 72 hours of tendency values can be viewed on the monitor [6]. The problem with the existing MP40 monitors is that they are connected in a closed Philips network which is only accessible within the operating room by using the Ixellence software. This software is only running on the Philips network and only enables a real-time viewing of the vital signs from the MP40 monitor to for example a laptop within the limited area around the operating room. At this moment, only a demo-version of the software is used and the IP-address of the monitor can not be reached from other computers in the hospital network. The MP40 monitor sends UDP packages that can not be forwarded by routers connecting the Philips network with a general or hospital network. This is illustrated in figure 1.

Figure 1 – Overview of network configuration at operating room

2.3 Research question

Besides the fact that the current Ixellence software is not able to interface the Philips MP40 monitor with the Hospital Information System, other factors raise the need to make an investigation about the storage of vital signs data into a central archive. This is because of the fact that not only the signals of the MP40 monitor will be stored, but the desired future situation is to store the signals at more care units from different monitors. Within the Hospital Italiano this system will be called a Signal Archive and Communication System or SACS [5]: computers or networks dedicated to the storage, retrieval, distribution and presentation of signals.

In general, the first objective of recording biomedical data is not to make a database but to monitor or diagnose a patient, or to do research. The recorded data strongly depends on this objective. For instance, monitoring the vital signs of a patient in acute life-threatening situations or being under surgical procedures requires online analysis and immediate visualization to allow immediate intervention. When data is recorded for research or diagnosis, then immediate visualization of analyzed data is usually not required, but continuous storage of data is.

Several reasons for the continuous storage of data can be given. The first important factor that drives the need for storage is the one for liability reasons. For example the United States does have a reputation regarding the 'claiming culture'. In case something happens during an operation, a patient is able to blame the surgeon or anesthetist and according to the law it can be decided that the patient gets a claim. Without an archive of signal data during the operation, it is difficult to prove that the physicians handled in the right manner. Although the culture in Argentina is different than the one in the United States, there is a trend moving towards the 'claiming culture' which raises the need for sufficient proof. Related to these liability issues is the second factor, namely the alarm notification. These notifications can, but also must be stored next to the signal data to be able to provide sufficient proof. Storage of alarms is impossible when using paper records.

The third factor that drives the need for storage given by the anesthetist is anesthesia performance measurement. By obtaining a set of averaged values from different surgeries, like the tendency values provided by the MP40 monitor, it is possible to obtain a measure linked to the performance. Fourth, precious physician time can be saved when automatically connecting medical device data. For example, the overall process which includes walking from bed to bed, manually collecting data and transcribing parameters into the patient records takes 2 to 3 minutes per device for 10 to 20 times each day. For a 50 bed care unit 12.000 up to 36.000 nursing hours per year can be saved or 49.000 up to 146.000 nursing hours per year for a 200 bed unit.

The mentioned drivers lead to the following set of requirements for the SACS:

- Easy data integration: the different output formats from different modalities and different vendors must be stored in the SACS.
- The data format for storage must preferably be a recognized international standard.
- The signals stored in the SACS must be viewed via the HIS. Therefore the SACS must be interoperable with the current HIS.
- Post processing of the stored signals must be possible.
- It must be possible to store annotations and alarm events together with the signal.

This report will present an independent recommendation about the possibilities to develop and integrate a SACS system within the current hospital environment. Therefore the objective of the research will be as follows:

‘Make a recommendation about the current possibilities for the Hospital Italiano to store the vital signs into an archive by making an extensive inventory of the suitable options’.

2.4 Working method

The actual need for the storage of the signals is raised at the operating room for the Philips MP40 monitor. However, the report will start from a broader perspective taking all the care units and monitors into account. At first general information about the storage of biomedical signals will be given together with an overview of already existing databases. The next step, provided in chapter 4, is the selection of monitors and care units within the Hospital Italiano that seem suitable for integration. Depending on the requirements and demands from the physicians it is predicted that it is not necessary to store all the available signs from all the monitors within the hospital.

After this inventory, the possibilities enabling the integration will be presented. Each possibility will be examined in order to be able to give a well-considered advice. A schematic overview of the working method is given in figure 1.

Figure 2 – Schematic overview of working method

2.5 Dataflow analyses

To show the difference in working method in the work of the physician a schematic analyses of the workflow on the neonatology department will be provided. The analyses for the other departments will be comparable, depending on the amount of data written on paper or already digitally stored. The exact way of working depends on the future functions of the SACS system, but schematically the desired dataflow situation can be made clear.

2.5.1 Current and future situation

Figure 3 shows the current situation of the dataflow on the neonatology department. For the most critical care children, the temperature, oxygen saturation, non-invasive and invasive blood pressure values are measured [7]. These values are written on a paper data sheet once every two hours. After the patient is released from the hospital, the paper archive will be stored for six months within the hospital to be able to review the data. When the patient has not returned within these months, the paper archive will be sent to the company AdeA, which takes care of the long term data storage for 10 years.

Figure 3 – Dataflow analyses Neonatology department Hospital Italiano – current situation

In figure 4 the desired future situation is given. It can be seen that all the information can be stored digitally, without manually writing the data from the bedside equipment on paper records. Keeping the set of requirements in mind, this also enables the post-processing of the stored signals and will even reduce the amount of nursing hours.

Figure 4– Dataflow analyses Neonatology department Hospital Italiano – desired future situation

2.5.2 Experiences with PACS

In some ways the development of the SACS system is comparable to a PACS system. Because of the fact that still no experiences with SACS systems exist, the experiences using PACS can be kept in mind.

Physician time can be saved by storing the information digitally. In stead of writing the paper records every two hours in the desired situation the desired signals will be stored automatically every two hours. However, in practice this seems not that easy. Many departments that introduced PACS and thus made the transition to filmless operation have discovered that although they are saving money by reducing costs associated with film as well as providing improved image access for clinicians, they are not achieving overall cost savings or improvements in either radiologist or staff productivity. This reflects differences in the type of PACS that is used, but also in the effectiveness with which the PACS is used as a tool to redesign departmental workflow [8]. According to the authors of the article, one of the most common mistakes made by facilities with PACS has been to underestimate the critical importance of the role PACS can play in the redesign of departmental work flow and enterprise-wide workflow. Without proper integration of this tool into the departmental workflow or reinvention of the work flow process in the department, the potential gains associated with the use of PACS cannot be realized.

3. Storing biomedical signals

In many hospitals many medical devices are already installed and daily used by medical and paramedical staff. The devices will be normally used till the end of their depreciation period, due to the fact that their replacement with modern and technological advanced ones is often not feasible [9]. Besides that, most of the existing devices were chosen before the integration with a Hospital Information System was a major requirement. Nowadays Hospital Information Systems for the storage of patient data are commonly used, but in many cases picture and signal data are not stored or do not have an interface with the HIS. In the following paragraphs an overview will be given of about the challenge of storing the biomedical signals on the basis of examples of already existing databases.

3.1 The challenge of storing biomedical signals

The most important challenges in the storage of biomedical signals can be divided in the properties of the existing medical devices and the data types and signals involved.

3.1.1 Differences in medical devices

Medical devices operate in various ways and many distinctions can be made. Some can use the store & forward principle while others use real-time data transfer. Equipment can differ in communication channels and protocols, their different data formats which are often proprietary and thus only available for equipment of the same provider. Sometimes the reluctance of manufacturers to provide information on protocols and data format can be a problem and some other times the poor correctness of the provided documentation due to complex project design choices.

3.1.2 Signals and data types

Also a lot of options exist on the signal storage itself. The accuracy of a biomedical signal measurement is often not higher than three decimals due to various reasons, for example the imprecise placement of the measurement sensor or electrode [10]. In most cases the dynamic range of the measurements can be covered by a 16-bit integer value in case of proper amplification. In some measurements, 8 bits are enough and 50% of the storage space can be saved if the format supports 8-bit integers.

A floating point number is a numerical-representation system in which a string of bits represents a real number. Although biomedical signals are hardly sampled as floating-point numbers, the need can arise to store intermediate analysis results along with the original signal. In this case, storage in a floating point data type may be necessary.

The size of a signal data file consists most of the signal information itself, especially in long-term measurements. However, in the case of long-term measurements signals are often analyzed by a physician or a computer and in that case also the need to store the results of this analysis occurs. These are called annotations. Annotations can for example be given in textual form and can be linked to certain time instances in the recording or they can form a summary annotation at the end of the recording, usually a diagnostic statement. Besides this diagnostic statement, the storage of alarm signals and other types of vital signs in the form of numeric measurements can also be important for storage. The alarm signals can be of legal importance in anesthesia recordings while the challenge in the storage of numeric measurements is that they are made at irregular intervals and therefore can not be stored as a separate biosignal channel.

Another factor that must be kept in mind is that not every signal will be stored with the same sampling frequency due to differences in change of rate. For example, the heart rate can be sampled at a much lower frequency than ECG [11]. More information about this is given in paragraph 8.2.

3.2 Examples of signal storage

By choosing a suitable file format and standard, the factors mentioned in paragraph 3.1 must be kept in mind. In literature, several examples of signal storage databases exist. A few of them will be presented below. These databases are selected on the basis of a literature research. A distinction is made between examples of the signal transfer itself between modality and database and examples of existing (critical-) care databases.

3.2.1 Existing critical care databases

In 2001 four critical care databases were available to the public [12]. These are the MGH/MF Waveform database from the Massachusetts Foundation, the Multi-parameter Intelligent Monitoring for Intensive Care (MIMIC) of the Beth Israel Hospital in Boston, the Improving Control of Patient Status in Critical Care (IMPROVE) at the Kuopio University Hospital in Finland and Improved monitoring for Brain dysfunction in Intensive care and Surgery (IBIS).

The databases consist of data recorded from the intensive care units, the operating room or other ECG studies. All the signals in the databases are 2- or 3-channel ECG recordings and include Systemic Arterial Pressure (SAP) and Pulmonary Arterial Pressure (PAP) hemodynamics measurements. Annotations including patient alarms, beat labels, patient state and free text are also included in the databases. Only the IMPROVE and IBIS database includes EEG signals and the length of the signal recordings varies from 3 hours to 48 hours. The used dataformat is for the MGH/MF and the MIMIC database MIT-BIH, which is a dataformat developed by the hospital itself, but the IMPROVE and IBIS databases use the common EDF format (see paragraph 9.2.4) and ASCII formats.

For three reasons, they faced challenges in building the databases. The first reason is that the data collection always comes on the second place, which means that the routine patient monitoring and support devices need to be attached as usually and the required therapy will be given without caring the data collection project. The collection of artifact-free data for example can be difficult in those cases. The second reason is that the technical properties of the recording devices not always satisfy the scientific requirements and always the same equipment, electrode placement and sampling rates must be used. The third reason is only applicable for the critical care database, since it is difficult to predict the timing of patient admission and therefore sufficient equipment must be available in order to store the signals. Sometimes also consent for the study is necessary from the patient and/or the relatives which can delay the start of the recording, which can be valuable. Therefore data collection in critical care will not likely be a well controlled study, but more a comprehensive documentation which also marks the main differences between critical care databases and other biomedical signal databases.

3.2.2 Physiological data acquisition system and database for disease dynamics

The Oregon Health Sciences University in Portland developed a physiological data acquisition system and database for the study of disease dynamics in the intensive care unit [11]. The study of the disease dynamics itself is not interesting for this report, but the used system can be a surplus value. The used system consisted of four main

components: 16 Philips Merlin patient monitors, a patient data server (PDS) that collects the signals from the monitors, a data storage workstation from Hewlett Packard connected via a LAN to the PDS that converts the signals to text files and to archive the files on CD-ROM and a Laboratory for Computational Neuroscience connected via the internet with the data storage workstation and the PDS.

The Philips monitors all had anti aliasing filters to the raw analog signal, they performed analog to digital conversion and formed discrete-time series of the continuous time signal. The researchers have chosen to limit the sampling rates by the monitor to three different values; slow varying signals like heart rate are sampled at 0.98Hz, the ECG at 500Hz to capture the high-frequency QRS-complex and all other signals at 125Hz to conserve data storage space.

The data was stored in ASCII format and once stored the data is preprocessed with software written for Matlab. At the end they have successfully recorded real-time continuous time series data from more than 170 patients. The data was imported and stored in physiologic databases organized by specific disease states. Reported limitations are the routine patient care activities that often interfere with accurate signal acquisition as a result of for example motion artifacts. Also the technical properties of the sensors, the bedside monitors or the recording system resulted in less than ideal data. Although there is no direct solution to isolating artifacts, but clinical annotations by an observer is probably the most accurate. The IMPROVE database is an example of a database with detailed annotations.

3.2.3 Storing Data from medical devices in e-Health applications

In 2004, the Foundation for Research and Technology in Greece (FORTH) integrated medical devices into an e-health platform [9]. Therefore it was necessary to integrate the different software components from each device by different parsing techniques. The integrated devices include a commercial electronic stethoscope, a vital signs monitor, a hand held spirometer, cardiographs and various radiology modalities. The vital signs monitor is connected via a RS232 cable to the e-health platform. The e-health platform supports the SCP-ECG standard for cardiographs also supporting that format and working according the store & forward principle. For the developed e-health device, also continuous ECG recordings were used in order to communicate in real-time. For this communication, together with the storage of the stethoscope and spirometer signals no standard data format is used. After the storage of the data, it was necessary to make every snapshot clearly identifiable. Therefore they made use of SCP like solutions to assure uniformity in demographic data and storage structure. The ECG section of the SCP data format could not be used, but the general structure was successfully used as a 'container'.

4. Selection of monitors

In addition to the information given in paragraph 2.3, it is necessary to exclude some of the available equipment in the Hospital Italiano for the integration with a future signal archiving system for three reasons. First, it takes too much time for this survey to make an inventory of all the monitors and how they give off the physiological signal. In total there are ± 230 monitors available in the Hospital Italiano [13]. Second, no network connection has to be made with monitors unable to measure signals needed by a physician and third only monitors available on a care unit that the hospital wants to be integrated in the future database have to be involved. Fourth, the Hospital Italiano can not integrate all the equipment at once and should start at the place where storage has a surplus value to the delivery of care and the other reasons mentioned in paragraph 2.3. For example, one can imagine that it is unnecessary to store for example one single blood pressure of a digital blood pressure cuff on the psychiatry unit. In that case, the psychiatric patients should be excluded which automatically excludes the psychiatric care unit and the monitors available in that specific department. In the following paragraph, the selection will be made on a comparable way.

4.1 Patients

The patient groups in the hospital can in general be divided into two groups which are inpatient and outpatient. An outpatient is a patient who visits a healthcare facility for diagnosis or treatment without spending the night in the same healthcare facility. In the selection, patients arriving at the emergency department will in first instance be viewed as outpatients. When a hospital stay or surgery is required, the patient will change group automatically. Besides the inpatient and outpatient group, one subgroup is assigned. This is the 'surgery' group which can either be in- or outpatients and which makes it more easily to separate between integration of all the monitors or only the monitors available at the surgery room.

However, to exclude patient groups and thus care units, a distinction is made between high and low risk patients on the basis of the information of the American Society of Anesthesiologists classes (ASA-) that can be seen in table 1 [14].

Class	Physical status	Mortality
ASA 1	Normally health patient	0,08%
ASA 2	Patient with mild systemic disease with no functional limitations	0,27%
ASA 3	Patient with moderate systemic disease with functional limitations	1,90%
ASA 4	Patient with severe systemic disease that is a constant threat to life	7,80%
ASA 5	Moribund patient who is not expected to survive another 24 hours with or without surgery	9,40%

Table 1 – American Society of Anesthesiologists classes

It can be seen that patients in ASA classes 4 and 5 have a strongly increased mortality rate. On the basis of this information, it is decided that only signals from patients in classes 4 and 5 will be stored. In the Hospital Italiano there are different locations where patients in the ASA classes 4 and 5 are situated. An overview of them is given in table 2, categorized in inpatients and outpatients and patients during surgery.

Inpatient	Outpatient	Surgery
Cardiac ICU*	Adult ER**	Ambulatory SR***
Neonatology ICU	Pediatric ER	Central SR
Adult ICU		Orthopedic SR
Pediatric ICU		

Table 2 – Location of selected patients in hospital; *ICU = Intensive Care Unit, **ER = Emergency Room, *SR = Surgery Room.**

In paragraph 4.3 the final selection of monitors will be made. First, it is necessary to select the minimum amount of vital signs that the monitors must be able to measure.

4.2 Important vital signs

Vital signs are measurements of the body's most basic functions and characteristic for these signs is that they can be measured over time in order to obtain a graph or a set of numerical values reflecting the health state of a patient. At least the four basic vital signs should be measured in order to be able to assess the most basic body functions [15]. These vital signs are the body temperature, heart rate, blood pressure and respiratory rate. Besides the basic set of vital signs, many other patient related signals can be measured with the existing equipment including ECG, EEG, EMG or CVP (central venous pressure), ICP (intracranial pressure), LAP (left atrial pressure), RAP (right atrial pressure) or PAP (pulmonary arterial pressure).

The ECG signal is most likely the most important signal and will definitely be used in all three care units. For example, it can be functional for the hospital to store an ECG from outpatient patients in case that during a normal health check (probably at another care unit as well) a heart problem appears. In this case, it can be helpful to store the ECG data for future visits of that patient. For inpatient patients it can also be of legal importance to store at least the ECG signal and non invasive blood pressure [5]. In case a patient dies the hospital is able to prove that they did everything to prevent it and did not ignore alarm signals. Obviously alarm signals must be saved as well in this case.

Because of the fact that at this moment the need for signal storage is the highest at the operating room, it is recommendable for the Hospital Italiano to focus on the signals necessary during operation and to integrate these signals in a future signal archive in a stepwise manner. Therefore the minimum required vital signs to control the anesthesia (during operation) are the electrocardiogram (ECG), the oxygen saturation of blood, invasive and noninvasive blood pressure values and arterial pressure [5]. When the patient is put under narcosis, also a carbon dioxide measurement is necessary. Besides these signals, it is also necessary to store annotations and alarm signals. Other patient related information, for example notes about the body temperature or blood pressure can easily be stored in the Hospital Information system.

4.3 Selection of monitors

After the selection of care units and vital signs an overview is given of the monitors available within the Hospital Italiano at the care units mentioned in table 2. The numbers in the left column represent the *total* amount of the monitors present in the hospital. However, almost all of the monitors are present at the care units given in the right column. The monitors not available at those care units are located at the San Justo location of the hospital.

#	Available monitors	Care Unit
25	Hewlett Packard 7835x	Cardiac ICU
16	Datascope passport x	Neonatology ICU, Adult ICU, Pediatric ICU
17	S&W Diascope II	Neonatology ICU, Pediatric ICU
12	Siemens SC6002	Neonatology ICU, Adult ICU, Pediatric ICU
20	GE Dash 4000	Neonatology ICU, Adult ICU, Pediatric ICU, Ambulatory SR, Central SR, Orthopedic SR
24	Philips MP40	Neonatology ICU, Adult ICU, Central SR, Orthopedic SR
14	Philips MP20	Neonatology, Central SR, Adult ER
6	Omega 1000-220	Pediatric ICU
2	S&W 5100	Pediatric ICU
5	Dyne MCD300	Pediatric ICU, Adult ER
1	Bicore CP100	Pediatric ICU
1	SM 8101	Pediatric ICU
1	Ohio BP2205	Pediatric ICU
2	Ohmeda CPU	Pediatric ICU
3	Camino MPM-1	Adult ICU, Pediatric ICU
2	Nellcor 4000 CP	Ambulatory SR
8	Siemens Sirecust 404-1	Ambulatory SR
1	Novamatrix 2010	Central SR
2	Philips M1026B	Orthopedic SR
4	Philips C1	Adult ER
5	Philips VM4	Pediatric ER

Table 3 – Overview of monitor brand and type available at the different care units. The Hewlett Packard 7835x series represents the Hewlett Packard 78352C and the Hewlett Packard 78354C monitor and the Datascope passport x series represents the passport LT and passport EL monitor.

The monitors given in table 3 can roughly be divided in 2 parts. The first 7 listed monitors from the HP 7835x series to the MP20 monitor are available on several care units or are widely available within the hospital. The other monitors are less available and sometimes old-dated, like the Siemens Sirecust 404-1 which is bought in the year 1993 [13]. Besides the limited timeframe of this survey, it is also not recommended to put effort into the integration of these monitors due to the following reasons. It can take a lot of time and effort and therefore also money to write a communication protocol only applicable for one monitor. It is conceivable that the monitor will be replaced before a signal archive is reality and therefore it is not feasible to try to integrate it at this moment. For these monitors, the focus can better be put on the purchase process of the next generation of equipment that is able to communicate with the preferred data formats. In case effort will be put in the connectivity of the monitor, there is a chance

that the data format is not interchangeable and therefore has no added value. Switching to another data format in the future can lead to great expenses. Besides that, it is possible that a whole new physical network must be installed in order to connect the monitor which also causes additional costs.

However, exceptions exist for the Philips M1026B, C1 and VM4 monitors. This is newer equipment, bought by the Hospital Italiano in January 2007 and from the same supplier as the MP40 and MP20. It can therefore easily be adopted in the ongoing research. The next step in this survey will be the investigation how the given monitors can be integrated with a future signal archive. Therefore chapters 6, 7 and 8 will provide information about existing medical connectivity solutions dealing with software for the integration of monitors.

6. Solution 1: Connectivity software

The first solution available to store the signals provided by the selected monitors is to make use of an integral solution provided by software suppliers. These suppliers are specialized in connecting several brands of bedside equipment in order to guarantee the signal storage. The Healthcare Information and Management Systems Society (HIMSS) is an organization exclusively focused on providing global leadership for the optimal use of information technology in healthcare [16]. During their annual conference in 2007, several companies showed their activities regarding the interoperability problems faced in healthcare. An overview of them will be given below.

6.1 CapsuleTech

CapsuleTech Technologie not only claims, but also is the world's number one provider for medical data integration. It is a private company and founded in 1997 in France. It established a market lead through its suite of hardware and software products and its expertise in device protocols and firmware. In November 2007 CapsuleTech won a performance award from Deloitte Technology Fast 500 which is a ranking of the fastest growing technology companies in Europe, the Middle East and Africa [17].

The main product of CapsuleTech is the DataCaptor Interface Server, see figure 3.

Figure 5 – CapsuleTech's illustration to promote their product

The DataCaptor Interface server manages the communication with the medical devices. The medical devices are connected to the DataCaptor network using DataCaptor ID Modules and Terminal Servers, or via serial cables or a LAN connection in case the specific device supports a network connection. They can be integrated directly into a clinical application by using an Application Program Interface (API). The API sends the data at the same rate it is output from the device. The host application then determines what data to accept and handles data formatting.

The DataCaptor Interface server has two optional add-ons, these are the Data Management Module server (DMM-server) and the Data Portal. The DMM-server enables the translation of device data to XML and HL7 ORU messages (which are

compliant with HL7 standard versions 2.0-2.3), it makes it possible to specify the frequency with which variables and values will be sent to a client application, it filters redundant data and applies tags for device and variable types. The Data Portal can forward the collected data via TCP/IP to non-Windows based applications.

The ID-modules and Terminal Servers are the connection between the medical devices and the DataCaptor Interface server. The ID-modules support the automatic detection and identification of each medical device when they are connected or reconnected. The Terminal Server handles like a HUB for all the ID-modules and uses RS232-to-Ethernet terminal servers to send the device data via TCP/IP [53].

The DataCaptor Interface server, the DataPortal and the DMM-server can support up to 130 devices when using a Windows XP based 500Mhz Pentium III Intel compatible system with 256Mb RAM and a 10Mbps internet connection. The average bandwidth used per device interface is 1.1 Kb/sec, but increases while using waveform information. In table 4 an overview is given of the selected devices within the Hospital Italiano that are supported by CapsuleTech.

Supported Monitors
Siemens SC6002
GE Dash 4000
Philips MP40 (M8003A)

Table 4 – Overview of monitors supported by CapsuleTech

6.2 Cardiopulmonary Corp.

The Cardiopulmonary Corporation (CPC) designs, develops and distributes the Bernoulli Enterprise Management System software and telemedicine solutions [18]. The Bernoulli system uses web-based network technology to interface with medical devices that have RS232 or Ethernet devices. It is also a data storage and retrieval application and allows clinicians to view the Bernoulli data, including waveform displays using computers and remote locations.

Figure 6 – Cardiopulmonary Corp’s illustration to promote their product

In table 5 an overview is given of the selected devices within the Hospital Italiano that are supported by Cardiopulmonary Corp.

Supported Monitors
GE Dash 4000
Philips MP40 (M8003A)

Table 5 – Overview of monitors supported by Cardiopulm. Corp.

6.3 Sensitron

Sensitron is a company specialized in wireless point of care solutions for the health care industry [19]. Although their main focus is on the wireless capturing of patient data at the bedside, it is worth to mention it. The current software used is called the ‘careTrends’ system that provides a structure for the integration of workflow, patient data and systems interfaces for the delivery of patient data which can be seen in figure 8. It enables the nurse to view all the vital signs measured at the bedside directly on a PDA not depending on the location. The data is converted into a single format that also is available to the EMR.

Figure 7 – Sensitron’s illustration to promote their product

6.4 Emergin

Emergin claims to be the leader in alarm and event management solutions for the business enterprise [20]. They help to streamline communications within the hospital, standardize work processes and ensure interoperability with third party vendors. Their main product is the Enterprise Service Bus (ESB) that provides standards-based integration across the enterprise; it collects, harmonizes, prioritizes and distributes real-time alarms and events. They provide adapters (which are an interoperability statement with third party vendors, like Dräger, GE and Philips) that help to migrate proprietary third party vendors to a common, standards-based XML format that is accessible in web-services. However, instead of connecting different patient monitoring systems, Emergin connects information systems. One of them is the Philips IntelliVue Information Center. More information is given in chapter 7.

7. Solution 2: Philips IntelliVue Information Center

Within the Hospital Italiano the newest and most advanced monitor in use is the Philips MP40 monitor. Since the need to store the biomedical signal data rose at the surgery room while using the MP40 monitor, in this chapter also the Philips networking solution will be discussed in more detail, because Philips itself also offers an extensive package of networking tools to connect the Philips equipment in the hospital [21].

The Philips networking solution is called the IntelliVue Information Center which can be seen in figure 6. This information center combines real-time monitoring with clinical

Figure 8 – Philips IntelliVue Information Center

decision support tools and is able to capture waveforms, trends, alarms and numerics from networked Philips patient monitors and telemetry systems. An extensive overview of the network structure can be seen in appendix 1. Below the most important options are mentioned.

A fully installed network consists of two main servers: the database server and the IntelliVue application server. The database server collects the physiological data from the IntelliVue monitors on the network or from the information in the IntelliVue Information Center to for example the Hospital Information System. The IntelliVue application server collects reference data from e.g. a PACS, laboratory information, Hospital Information Systems or the TraceMaster view program and sends it to the IntelliVue monitors or the IntelliVue Information Center. The TraceMaster program is a data management system for the processing, storage and distribution of ECG data. The standard edition of this software can store 500.000 ECG signals (with a frequency of 500Hz) and the enterprise edition up to 4 million ECG signals [22].

The main screen displays real-time waveforms, numerics and alarms for up to 16 patients on one display. Up to 32 waveforms can be displayed in either single or dual column formats. This construction makes the real-time monitoring and the decision support tools possible.

The IntelliVue M3150 Information Center software also provides short-term data storage up to 96-hours for 4 waveforms per patient including alarm records [23]. Waveforms can be exported as .PNG files for use in documentation systems like CareVue [24]. HL7 output is enabled. Recording options are available for the 50mm USB 2-channel recorder and the Philips 4-channel recorder. The USB 2-channel recorder has capabilities for up to two waveforms and 3 lines of annotation. The 4-channel Recorder can record up to four real-time waveforms on a 112mm strip.

Besides that, the M3150 software provides arrhythmia and ST-segment monitoring and has the capability to visually identify a patient in alarm and its severity on the main screen from the Information Center. Also audible alarm tones indicate the severity. Criteria for alarms and for storage and recording of events can be configured per Information Center.

8. Solution 3: In-house development

Besides solution one and two that can be bought as a package which will be fully installed and made operational by the supplier within the hospital, another option exists. This option is the in-house development of the SACS system which can be developed within the hospital on the same way as they did with the current HIS. Therefore it is necessary to interface in any case the MP40 monitor. Additional information about this is given in this chapter.

8.1 Philips IntelliVue MP40

The Philips IntelliVue MP40 monitor is a portable networked patient monitor within the Philips IntelliVue family. Other monitors in this range are the MP20 and MP30 for flexible care and patient transfer or the more advanced MP60, MP70 and MP80 monitor and the MP90 monitor for the most critical care patients [25]. The current problems regarding the integration and network connections with the current software are described in paragraph 2.2. Here more detailed information will be given about the data export interface of the monitor.

Figure 9 – Philips IntelliVue MP40 monitor

Data from the MP40 monitor can be transferred via the Local Area Network (LAN) or Medical Information Bus (MIB/RS232). The Data Export Interface via the LAN is not available when the IntelliVue monitor is connected to the Philips LAN, for example when used for the connection with the Philips Information Center. Communication via the MIB/RS232 Interface is always possible, but connection of other devices to the Philips LAN is only possible if the devices are approved by Philips [26].

The device can be connected by using a normal Ethernet switch or hub in the combination with UTP cables or directly to a computer by using a UTP cross over cable. The following data can be accessed from one of these interfaces:

- All measurement numerics and alarm-data (real-time update rates up to 1024ms)
- Wave data (depending on the type and configuration 2 ECG and 5 other waves or 3 ECG and 2 other waves)
- Patient demographic data entered by the user in the Intellivue monitor.
- IntelliVue monitor system data

8.1.1 Safety note

It is important to notice that when using in-house devices in the network infrastructure within the patient vicinity, the devices must comply with the IEC and EN international safety regulations regarding the patient safety. The patient vicinity is area is defined as the area within 1.85m of the perimeter of the patient's bed or within 2.3m of the floor. All external devices in the patient vicinity must comply with IEC 60601-1:1988/A1:1991/A2:1995 or EN 60601-1:1990 /A1:1993/A2:1995. The international IEC 60601-1 standard is the global benchmark, a norm for the comparison of product

performance, for medical electrical equipment and used for product registration, contract tenders and defense against claims in event of problems. The EN 60601-1 standard is used for medical electrical equipment and provides general requirements for safety.

8.2 Ixellence GmbH

The current software used to interface the Philips MP40 is the Ixellence software, provided by a German company. They develop customized software for technical and industrial applications including modular based software in medical telematics. All the configurations can be controlled by the person working with the software. One of the software products is the TrendFace system, which is a tool for the PC data acquisition and remote supervision of Philips patient monitors. It includes functions which record the vital parameters (like heart rate) and primary signals like ECG. The software transfers the data to a PC over a serial interface and saves all data and signal curves on the computer harddisk [27].

The TrendFace software exists of two different versions which are the TrendFace Solo and the TrendFace network. The TrendFace Solo software is able to interface one bed or monitor at a time and the signs that must be stored can be selected. In addition to this, the TrendFace network supports remote supervising and multi-monitoring with PC, laptop or PDA. The patient data can be evaluated at several computers at the same time, enabling physicians to have access to the monitors and to the patient data from everywhere in the hospital.

At this moment, the hospital works with a demo-version, but by obtaining a license more functions can be used. A one year license for one monitor costs €499,- and a one year license for a bundle €2.499,-.

8.3 Integrating the Healthcare Enterprise

When developing the SACS system in-house, many decisions must be made regarding data formats and storage technologies. One requirement for the SACS is that the data format for storage must be a recognized international standard to enable interoperability between databases of other hospitals. In case these databases consist of the same data format, there is interoperability between the databases. However, interoperability is also required for getting the signals into the database. This is another kind of interoperability, but with the focus on the connection between HIS and monitoring equipment. Since no one vendor makes all the devices that will eventually need to be connected, no single vendor solution is available and therefore no simple solution exists to integrate all the equipment. The IHE can provide some additional support in the decision making process regarding the dataformats and other standards

The Integrating the Healthcare Enterprise (IHE) is an initiative by healthcare professionals and industry to improve the way computer systems in healthcare share information [1]. IHE promotes the coordinated use of established standards such as HL7 and DICOM to address specific clinical needs in support of optimal patient care. Currently, the IHE is supported by the American College of Cardiology, the Healthcare Information and Management Systems Society and the Radiological Society of North America.

In some cases, IHE recommends selection of specific options supported by these or other standards [28]. However, IHE does not introduce technical choices that contradict conformance to these standards. If errors in or extensions to existing standards are identified, IHE's policy is to report them to the appropriate standards bodies for

resolution within their conformance and standards evolution strategy. IHE is therefore an implementation framework and not a standard itself.

IHE is organized by clinical and operational domains. In each domain, users with clinical and operational experience identify integration and information sharing priorities and vendors of relevant information systems develop consensus and standards-based solutions to address them. Each domain includes a technical committee, whose primary task is developing and documenting these solutions (known as integration profiles) and a planning committee, whose primary tasks are long-term scope planning and organization deployment activities such as testing events and educational programs. Besides that, each domain develops and maintains its own set of Technical Framework documents. At this moment, 10 Technical Frameworks exist.

The IHE Patient Care Device Technical Framework defines specific implementations of established standards to achieve integration goals for the Patient Care Device domain. Such integration promotes appropriate sharing of medical information to support optimal patient care. The Framework itself is a technical story, but it can help IT departments, clinical users and consultants to understand and address clinical integration needs and therefore enables information technology specialists to concentrate on improving the core functionality of systems, rather than developing and maintaining redundant, point-to-point interfaces.

8.4 Overview of signals

In case the hospital chooses the in-house solution the signals obtained from the medical equipment will be captured on a computer. In this chapter some additional information is given about how the equipment processes the raw signals as mentioned in paragraph 4.2, especially ECG.

8.4.1 Electrocardiogram (ECG)

The ECG is the electrical manifestation of the contractile activity of the heart, and can quite easily be recorded with surface electrodes on the limbs or chest. The ECG is perhaps the most commonly known, recognized and used biomedical signal. The rhythm of the heart in terms of beats per minute (bpm) may be easily estimated by counting the readily identifiable waves. More important is the fact that the ECG wave shape is altered by cardiovascular diseases and abnormalities such as myocardial ischemia and infarction, ventricular hypertrophy, and conduction problems. Therefore the ECG is an important analyzing tool.

Figure 10 – ECG signal

The ECG signal is obtained by recording the electrical activity of various points in the heart. In clinical practice, the 12 lead ECG is commonly used. The ECG-signal represents a few important steps. The first step in the ECG recording is the representation of the firing of the sinoatrial node (SA-node) which causes an electrical activity through the atrial musculature causing slow-moving depolarization of the atria. This causes contraction of the atria that in the ECG signal can be seen as the P-wave. The P-wave is a low-amplitude wave, with an amplitude of about 0.1 – 0.2mV and a duration of about 60 – 80ms. The excitation waves faces a propagation delay at the

atrioventricular node (AV-node), which results in a normally iso electric segment of about 60 – 80 ms. In this period of time the ventricles will be completely filled with blood arriving from the atria.

The His bundle, that splits in the right- and left bundle branches propagates the stimulus from the AV-node to the ventricles causing the ventricles to contract. This results in the QRS-complex which has an amplitude of about 1mV and a duration of 80ms. The plateau portion of the action potential causes a normally iso-electric segment of about 100 – 120ms after the QRS, known as the ST segment. The last part of the ECG is the T wave, which reflects the repolarization of the ventricles and has an amplitude of about 0.1 – 0.3mV and a duration of 120 – 160ms.

The raw ECG signal is often contaminated by noise and artifacts that can be within the frequency band of interest [29]. In order to extract useful information from the noisy ECG signal, the raw ECG signal needs to be processed. This signal processing can roughly be divided into two stages: preprocessing and feature extraction.

The preprocessing phase removes or suppresses noise from the raw ECG signal and the feature extraction stage extracts diagnostic information from the ECG signal.

Figure 11 – General ECG processing flowchart

8.4.1.1 Preprocessing the ECG signal

When defining the ECG disturbances into categories, the disturbances in general can be classified in five categories. These are the following:

- power line interference
- baseline wandering
- electrode pop or noise contact
- patient-electrode motion artifacts
- EMG noise

Among these noises, the power line interference and the baseline wandering are the most significant and have the most influence on the ECG signal. Usually the ECG signal acquisition hardware can remove the power line interference, but baseline

wandering and other wideband noises are not easily suppressed by hardware equipments. Baseline wandering means that the signal is not in line with the horizontal axis, but that it has the tendency to move up and down. An example of power line noise is given in figure 12. The noise becomes visible at the positive and negative peaks of the sine wave, due to a noisy device or line. The power line interference is narrow-band noise centered at 60 Hz (or 50 Hz) with a bandwidth of less than 1 Hz. It can be suppressed by using a lowpass filter.

Baseline wandering usually comes from respiration at frequencies between 0.15 and 0.3Hz. This can be suppressed by a high-pass digital filter or using the wavelet transform. A wavelet is a kind of mathematical function used to divide a given function, in this case the ECG signal, into different frequency components so each component can be studied with a resolution that matches its scale. The wavelet transform is the representation of a function by wavelets. The wavelet transform-based approach is usually better, because this approach introduces no latency and less distortion than the digital filter-based approach.

Figure 12 – Power line noise

8.4.1.2 Features Extraction

Features extraction is often necessary for the purpose of diagnosis. From the preprocessed data, QRS intervals, QRS amplitudes, PR intervals, ST intervals or fetal heart rates can be selected. For example the detection of R-peaks and the QRS-complexes provides information about the heart rate, conduction velocity, tissue conditions and various other abnormalities. However, the presence of noise and time-varying morphology makes the detection difficult. LabView provides a few toolkits that make this possible [29]. Another possibility they provide is the fetal EDG extraction by using Independent Component Analysis (ICA) or adaptive filtering.

8.4.2 Oxygen saturation

The oxygen saturation (SaO_2) is a relative measure of the amount of oxygen dissolved in blood. Besides the term SaO_2 also SpO_2 is used. However, SaO_2 refers to the oxygen saturation of arterial blood as measured by a CO-oximeter and SpO_2 refers to the oxygen saturation of arterial blood as measured by a pulse-oximeter [30]. The difference between them is that only a real CO-oximeter can determine an accurate value, since this oximeter is able to distinguish between different types of haemoglobins in blood. The pulse-oximeter only adjusts for this in the calculation and therefore always is an estimation of the real value.

The oxygen saturation must be kept within a given interval and must therefore be continuously monitored during the operation. The oxygen saturation measurement is based on a difference in wavelength received by the oximeter that transmits light usually through the finger. The receiver on the other side receives the analog signal and

then it can be processed by an analog or digital system to provide a result. Usually the noise and movement artifacts will be reduced during this process.

8.4.3 Arterial pressure

Arterial pressure is the name where general 'blood pressure' often refers to and is the pressure measured in the larger arteries. During an operation, also the main arterial pressure is important.

The arterial pressure can be measured by invasive and non-invasive blood pressure measurements. Invasive blood pressure is a method of measuring the blood pressure internally by using a catheter inserted into an artery. This provides continuous monitoring of arterial blood pressure with greater accuracy in patients with unstable blood pressures or hypotension. Improper damping and calibration account for a large percentage of the errors in the monitoring [31]. Non invasive blood pressure is the blood pressure measured by an (electronic) cuff which is placed around a patient's wrist and can be used to measure arterial blood pressure, central venous pressure and pulmonary artery pressure [32].

8.4.4 CO₂ measurement

The amount of carbon dioxide (CO₂) in the blood is measured during capnography. It directly reflects the elimination of CO₂ by the lungs and it indirectly reflects the production of CO₂ by tissues and the transport of CO₂ to the lungs. Modern CO₂ analyzers are based on the absorption of infrared light by CO₂ in a gas sample.

At this moment, the six vital signs (arterial pressure includes invasive, non-invasive and mean arterial pressure measurements) that are most important for storage are the ones listed above. However, every signal differs from the others and every signal is processed in a different way. The signal that differs most from the others is the ECG signal. In paragraph 8.4 an overview will be given of recommended sampling rates for the capturing of physiologic data.

8.5 Sampling of vital signs

Sampling rates must be chosen in such a way that the requirements of subsequent analysis are covered. Several articles exist regarding the sampling rate of capturing ECG data. Most of the articles deal with the measurement of heart rate variability (HRV) which is a promising quantitative marker of autonomic heart activity [33], but also other features extraction as mentioned in paragraph 8.3.1.2 are taken into account.

In general, all articles recommend using a sampling rate of at least 500Hz [33, 34, 35], but in some cases a sampling rate of 250Hz can be sufficient. This was calculated by using R-wave interpolation to detect the accuracy of R-wave occurrence time for different sampling rates [36]. Three different interpolation methods, namely linear, cubic, and spline were compared. Using the cubic interpolation a resolution of 1ms and deviation of ± 1 ms in more than 99% of the RR intervals was reported for the sampling rate of 250Hz. However, for the 100Hz sampling rate, the same resolution was preserved in 90.5% of the RR intervals. A too low sampling rate, for example 100Hz or less, may produce unwanted variations of the signal characteristics in the estimation of the onset point of the R wave which alters the spectrum considerably [33]. Therefore the Task Force of The European Society of Cardiology and The North American Society of Pacing and Electrophysiology recommends defines the optimal range between 250–500 Hz or even higher.

S. Ward et al. investigated the impact of different ECG sampling frequency choices on the PR interval time series and resulting spectra [34]. They conclude that since the noise power is inversely proportional to the sampling frequency squared, considerable improvement is made by moving from a sampling rate of 128 Hz up to 512 Hz. For further use sampling frequencies of 512 Hz or higher should be considered. These sampling rates may be implemented by direct sampling of the ECG or through interpolation methods.

The sampling rates for the other vital signs vary in literature and now recommended sampling rates were found. However, the minimal and optimal sampling rates as used during for digital polysomnography as the basis for automatic sleep scoring can serve as a guide [37]. These results are given in table 6.

Signal	Minimum sampling rate	Optimal sampling rate
Capnography	16 Hz	25 Hz
Oxygen saturation	0.5 Hz	1 Hz
ECG	100 Hz	250 Hz
Heart rate	1 Hz	4 Hz
Blood pressure	50 Hz	100 Hz

Table 6 – Minimal and optimal requirements for polysomnography

Notable is that the optimal sampling rate for the ECG measurement is 250Hz, whereas the recommendable sampling rate found in literature is at least 500Hz. One explanation could be that less resolution is necessary for sleep records, because no specific arrhythmias have to be detected.

In a study for the disease dynamics at the intensive care unit [11], the slowly varying signal averages such as heart rate, are samples at 0.98Hz. The others signals, like respiratory and pressure waveforms were measured at a sampling rate of 125Hz. These values are comparable with the ones given in table 6. In any case, it is important to remark that signal storage below the given frequencies is not recommended. Further processing of the signals is not possible or important information is missing.

9. Requirements for SACS

In this chapter some information related to the storage system itself will be given. It includes information about the legal issues that are important regarding the storage, but also an overview about available and commonly used standards will be given and the expected required storage capacity will be calculated.

9.1 Legal issues concerning storage

Many advantages of a fully working signal archive can be found in the systemic collection and use of electronic health data [38]. Better data availability allows physicians to make more informed decisions about health plans, diagnoses and treatments. This improves the clinical care through faster and more accurate diagnoses, increased checks on medical procedures, prevention of adverse drug events, instantaneous research of medical conditions and the dissemination of expert medical information to areas that are traditionally underserved. However, computerized databases of personally identifiable information may be accessed, changed, viewed or used more easily and by more people than paper-based records. As a consequence, along the mentioned benefits also significant legal challenges arise: who is allowed to see the signals, is the information stored in a safe database and is it possible to make the signals online available?

Hodge et al. describe three key areas regarding the legal protection of patients and providers for the use and disclosure of stored health information. These are 1) privacy of individually identifiable health information, 2) quality and reliability of information and 3) tort-based liability.

9.1.1 Privacy of health information

Protecting the privacy of personal health information is critical. Insufficient protections can lead to unauthorized use and disclosures of data that can lead to embarrassment, social stigma and discrimination of a patient. With little more than basic information about a person, detailed medical profiles of individuals can be assembled by private or commercial actors through online networks. For example for the use of e-mail messages in healthcare, The American Medical Informatics Association developed guidelines for the use of patient-physician e-mail that reflects the privacy values [39]. The first is to obtain patient informed consent before using e-mail for direct correspondence, the second is to explain and use security mechanisms, the third is to prohibit the forwarding of patient e-mail without express authorization followed by the fourth guideline that says that patients have to be informed about those having access to their messages and whether their messages will become part of their medical records. The fifth and sixth guideline say that messages must be responded responsibly and that references to third parties must be avoided. These guidelines can also be used for other communication methods instead of e-mail.

9.1.2 Quality and Reliability

The quality and reliability of personal medical information are related to the protection of privacy data in three ways [38]. First, the fair use of information, including the right to access and change medical records may lead to better quality data by allowing individuals to change erroneous information. Second, privacy assurances between physicians and patients enhance a trusting relationship between these parties. It is possible that patients who lack trust in healthcare providers may fail to disclose their medical conditions. This lowers the quality and reliability of health data. Finally,

national standards for data protection may encourage greater sharing of data. When physicians and others rely on accepted principles regarding disclosure and use of health information, a responsible circulation of health data can flow.

9.1.3 Tort-based liability

Literally, a tort means an injury to a person caused by another. In this case, tort-based liability is the liability a physician has for his patients. Unwarranted disclosures of personal medical information by physicians can result in claims of invasion of privacy, breach of confidentiality or even statutory violations under state law. The disclosure of information through media like e-mail or the internet would result in liability, but to assess the responsibility is difficult. To trace an electronic disclosure to a responsible party is difficult, especially when there is no adequate security trail and the information is published on the internet.

9.2 Need for standards

From paragraph 3.2 it becomes clear that a general-purpose, effective, user-friendly and universally accepted data format for the storage of medical signals is not available at this moment [10,41]. Therefore it is necessary to find a data format that suits the wishes and requirements of the hospital, but also one that can meet the foreseeable international market of third-party biosignals analysis and is thus supported by many manufacturers. In medical imaging, particularly in radiology, the DICOM/ MEDICOM standard is accepted both by American and European manufacturers and has already solved the interoperability problem, but in the biomedical signal domain various alternatives still exist. First, an overview will be given of four formats that are commonly used and supported by more than one institution in more than one country [10,9].

9.2.1 DICOM & DICOM Supplement 30

Besides the traditional focus of DICOM on medical images, in 1999 DICOM also introduced abilities for managing waveform data [42]. This is accomplished by defining new object types, called SOP classes. This is the abbreviation of Service-Object Pair classes. These SOP classes are the functional units of DICOM and consist of service classes and information objects. The information objects define the core contents of medical imaging and the service classes define what to do with those contents. DICOM has three SOP classes for ECG (12-lead, General ECG and Ambulatory ECG) and separate SOP Classes for hemodynamic waveforms. No SOP class is available for EEG data or a 'general purpose' waveform. The waveform data itself is organized into channels and channels with common groups are grouped together into Multiplex groups. Besides this core data, there is also space available for storing additional information, like patient information but also frequencies, calibrations and annotations.

This DICOM supplement 30 was developed after popular demand from the ECG community for purposes where biosignals are collected in connection with a medical imaging procedure. It is developed in accordance with the standard development process of the DICOM Standards Committee, but it includes changes to several parts of the original DICOM standard [43]. Originally, DICOM has had a rudimentary mechanism to interchange waveform data which is called the Curve Information Entity. This is used within the Standalone Curve Information Object and within other composite image objects. The Supplement follows the general approach of that capability, but refines it for the specific requirements of time-based waveforms, and makes its syntax and semantics more robust.

9.2.2 CEN/ENV 1064

The CEN/ENV 1064 standard is also known as the SCP-ECG standard and is widely available for ECG recordings [43]. SCP-ECG is supported by many major manufacturers of ECG equipment and is therefore a suitable format for ECG recordings. This standard can handle binary signals and annotations in a number of defined sections as they are obtained in different tests with ECG recordings. These include short-term ECG recordings, long-term ECG recordings, stress tests with ECG and also angiography with ECG. Data compression with known algorithms is also possible in the format. The signal characteristics including filter specifications, sampling rates and annotation codes are limited to ECG recording and therefore the data format can only be used for ECG databases.

9.2.3 ASTM 1467

ASTM 1467 is the only standard that is supported by an official standardization body. It has been prepared in cooperation with HL-7 and defines a message using the HL7 methodology. An advantage of this format is that it supports almost all neurophysiological measurements, but also for example ECG monitoring. The data format is able to store both primary and derived data. The primary data includes the digitized waveforms, but also for example filter settings, time stamps, sampling frequencies and transducer locations. Derived data can consist of derived measures entered by a physician or calculated by the device. An ASTM 1467 message consists of sequential series of segments, with each segment conveying one aspect of the message. The segments consist of fields that define one attribute of the segments. Also subfields exist. The data types that are defined by ASTM 1467 are special types of text strings, because the segments and fields are in ASCII characters. Disadvantages of using ASCII are that they require a lot of storage capacity and require a long search time in a database.

9.2.4 EDF

The EDF, which stands for European Data Format, is a simple format for exchange and archiving of multilingual times series which is not only necessarily biological data. It was originally developed by engineers coping with EEG signals during sleep. An EDF file has an ASCII header containing mainly patient and time identification, the number of signals and the technical characteristics. The header is followed by subsequent data records. An important advantage of the EDF is that the studying and the implementation of an EDF import/export unit takes only a few days of work. Research groups in Europe, Australia and the United States have already implemented it.

9.2.5 CEN-TC251/FEF

This file exchange format for vital signs (FEF) is based on the CEN-TC251/WGIV model and on a lot of biomedical measurements. The model was developed to incorporate data from intensive care units, anesthesia departments and clinical laboratories including neurology. This also leads to a disadvantage of this format, because of its increased complexity. A biosignal in FEF format consists of sections; each section has a tag in the beginning for the receiving application to identify each section. The tag is followed by a length field that indicates the length of the section and the data itself. The sections itself are for example the demographic-, healthcare provider- and medical device section and each contains specific information. There is

also a so called session archive, in which links to images or videos and alarm data can be stored.

Besides the four mentioned data formats, also other data formats show up. Most of these data formats are not only able to handle ECG signals, but are developed in order to be applicable for every biomedical signal. Two of them that often appear in literature will be explained in some more detail below. One of them is a part of DICOM. DICOM is the third version of a standard developed by the American College of Radiology (ACR) and the National Electrical Manufacturers Association (NEMA). It already turned out to be a central standard in radiology and it is increasingly used in other medical fields [41,45]. The DICOM standard involves several layers for the communication of messages as well as the storage of image files. In 1999 an active cooperation with Health Level 7 started to establish a DICOM-HL7 working group. HL7 is a standard that addresses the exchange of clinical and administrative data. HL7 is also widely used in hospitals all over the world [44].

9.2.6 MFER

The aim of MFER (Medical waveform description Format Encoding Rules) is to encode medical waveforms such as ECG, EEG, respiration curves and various other data, which are sampled at a certain frequency, interval or distance [46]. MFER has two major components which are sampling information and frame information. The sampling information consists of two attributes which are sampling frequency and sampling resolution. The frame information describes how the waveform data is aligned, and it has three major components which are data block, channel and sequence [47].

MFER aims at providing a method to efficiently encode only medical waveforms so that the encoded data may be collected in a database to be used for clinical and research purposes, independent of a specific data storage or network. Therefore MFER itself recommends future users that it is desirable to use MFER only for encoding medical waveforms. Patient information or observation data should be managed by the database management system.

9.3 Storage technologies

For the storage of patient information, including personal information, images and signals, there are a number of options for choosing the right storage technology [48]. Storage is usually classified as either online, nearline or offline. Online storage refers to data that is stored on magnetic hard drives with access times in milliseconds and transfer rates in the range of 10 to several 100.000 megabytes per second. This type of storage is immediately available to any type of database. Nearline storage refers to a tape or optical jukebox in which robotic arms can retrieve the tapes automatically and insert them into a drive to read or write the data. A nearline storage device can usually access data within 60 seconds and is able to transfer data with a few MB/sec. The last type of storage technology is offline storage. This can be a removable type or optical media that is stored on a shelf in a catalog and is retrieved manually. The need for offline storage devices is decreasing, because of the increasing online and nearline storage capacities, the slow retrieval of data and the chance of data loss due to misplacements or mishandles.

Choosing the most flexible, robust and cost-effective storage capacity is hospital dependent. It is necessary to make an inventory consisting of the available budget, the expected required storage capacity and a look into the future. Since 1952 there has been a sustained average annual growth in capacity of 33% and in the near future there are

higher capacity drives at lower prices. To obtain the best results, it is preferable to use online storage and there are three ways of using online storage for archiving systems: direct attached storage (DAS), storage area network (SAN) and network attached storage (NAS). DAS is to have the hard drives directly on the server running the archiving application. This is the simplest model and the model which all PACS vendors started with, but these systems face scalability problems in a PACS environment in which it is necessary to use lots of drives. More popular solutions are the SAN and NAS. The SAN is a dedicated network for connecting storage devices to computers that can be accessed from more than one server. This means that it is possible to add storage each year without having to take the servers down. NAS is not directly attached to the servers and the storage is accessed using network standard protocols. An important advantage of NAS is that it is not tightly coupled to a vendor which makes it possible to use general hard- and software and therefore it does not need the same level of validation with the archiving application for every upgrade.

Described above is the way how storage devices like hard disks and or CD-ROMs can be connected in order to obtain a storage network. A system for the storage of signals can use exactly the same network structure or hardware. In this manner, there is no difference between a picture- and a signal archiving system. The capacity of the storage device depends on the amount and length of the signal files that will be stored.

9.4 Required Storage Capacity

The required storage capacity is dependent on many aspects, like the amount of monitors connected to SACS, the amount of signals measured, the resolution of the measurement and the time that the signal is recorded. Therefore it is quite complicated to make a detailed calculation of the required storage capacity and as a consequence two estimations will be made. The estimations vary from a relatively simple solution to an extensive solution.

9.4.1 Minimal Required Capacity

The simple solution in this case is the solution from CapsuleTech. CapsuleTech supports the Siemens SC6002, the GE Dash 4000 and the Philips MP40 monitor within the Hospital Italiano and in total there are 56 monitors available within the hospital (see table 3). It is assumed that when one of the mentioned solutions will be chosen, no less monitors will be connected to the SACS.

The monitors are available on the Intensive Care Units and the Operation Room. The minimum amount of data is stored at the neonatology department [7, 49] where once every two hours 4 types of signals are stored. The calculation below shows the database capacity that is minimally necessary at the neonatology department when a SACS system with 16 bit storage (see paragraph 3.1.2) is used for 6 months within the hospital.

Signal	Sampling rate	Accuracy	Time	Bitrate
Body temperature	1 Hz	16 bit	1 second	= 16 bit /s
NIBP	100 Hz	16 bit	1 second	= 1600 bit /s
IBP	100 Hz	16 bit	1 second	= 1600 bit /s
Oxygen saturation	1 Hz	16 bit	1 second	= 16 bit /s

Table 7 – Required signals for minimal capacity

When the signals at the neonatology department are stored once every two hours, just one sample will be stored every time. One sample is 16 bit, thus 12 times a day storing 4 signals (64 bit) gives $12 * 64 = 768$ bit = $768 / 8 = 96$ byte for one monitor every day. For 56 monitors this gives $96 \text{ byte} * 56 = 5184$ byte = 5.18kb per day. For half a year this makes $5.18\text{kb} / \text{day} * 183 \text{ days} = \mathbf{948,7kb}$.

However, this is not streaming data and no ECG signal is stored in this case. When every signal will be stored for 1 minute and 10 minutes of ECG data will be stored every day, the following calculation applies:

The table shows a bit stream of 3232 bits per second in total, thus 12 times a day recording for 60 seconds gives $3232 * 12 * 60 = 2.327.040$ bits = 258.560 bytes per day for 1 monitor. Adding the ECG signal for 10 minutes makes $258,6\text{kb} + (500 \text{ samples} / \text{second} * 16 \text{ bits} * 600 \text{ seconds}) / 8 = 858,56\text{kb}$ per day. Storage for 6 months requires $858,56\text{kb} * 183 \text{ days} = 157,12\text{Mb}$ of harddisk space for 1 monitor, thus for 56 monitors it makes **8,8Gb**.

9.4.2 Maximum Required Capacity

The extensive solution in this case is the solution where all signals from all monitors will be stored. For the convenience of the calculation, the signals to be stored are presented in table 8. Every signal will be stored 24 hours a day for half a year for every available monitor within the hospital. The total amount of selected monitors is 171 (see table 3).

Signal	Sampling rate	Accuracy	Bitrate
Body temperature	1 Hz	16 bit	= 16 bit /s
Blood pressure	100 Hz	16 bit	= 1600 bit /s
Heart rate	4 Hz	16 bit	= 64 bit /s
Oxygen saturation	1 Hz	16 bit	= 16 bit /s
ECG	500 Hz	16 bit	= 8000 bit /s

Table 8 – Required signals for maximal capacity

The table shows a total bitrate of 9696 bites per second, which is equal to 1212 bytes per second. 24 hour storage gives $1212 * 24 \text{ hours} * 60 \text{ minutes} * 60 \text{ seconds} = 104.716.800$ bytes = 104,72 Mb a day. For 171 monitors the required capacity is $17,91\text{Gb}$ a day and for half a year $183 * 17,91\text{Gb} = \mathbf{3,3Tb}$.

10. Look into the future

Irrespective of the choice between the three given connectivity solutions, before making a decision the situation within and outside the hospital must be kept in mind. In this chapter, a closer look will be taken into the changing society and the equipment of the future, but also the possible features of the SACS system, based on interviews with health care professionals. Paragraph 10.3 pays attention to a special wish from the hospital.

10.1 Changing society & Improving equipment

As mentioned in paragraph 2.3, the most important driver for the Hospital Italiano at this moment for the storage of signals is for legal issues. This is in agreement with the general drivers for the development of healthcare [50]. These general drivers can be subdivided into demographic changes, cultural diversities, an open society, IT developments and consumerism. Demographic changes are for example the upcoming presence of chronic diseases, age related diseases and co morbidity. Consumerism refers to the fact that patients more and more behave like a client or customer and are willing to make conscious informed choices, also in healthcare. To anticipate on these changes, the healthcare sector is dealing with issues like transparency, governance, quality and safety, but it is also developing seamless services and improving the network quality. The storage of signals can be an important issue in for example the improvement of transparency.

Besides these drivers on the management level, also technical improvements will eventually enable and lead to signal storage. A lot of devices have not previously been connected into a network, because they were too mobile and therefore not suitable to connect with an intranet connection [51]. Nowadays more and more devices, like infusion pumps, patient monitors and ventilators are getting wireless connectivity for example using the Bluetooth technology. This is one technology that can enable wireless transfer of vital signs within a hospital.

All together, these are indications that in the future more emphasis will be put on the storage of signals although it will of course take years before all hospitals have fully integrated picture and signal storage systems. Also in future storage systems, selections of monitors suitable for storage must be made, but increasing needs together with newer techniques will simplify this process.

10.2 SACS features

It can be imagined that there are many ways of how to use the future signal archive. It is clear that there will be a harddisk with signals stored on it, but there can be many varieties in the way they are stored and measured at the patient's bedside. In this report no specific advice will be given, due to the variety of cases. For example, by measuring the signals at the bedside of a patient at the Adult ICU lying there for an unknown period of time, some variables can influence the way the signals will be stored:

- condition of the patient
- the post-processing process of the signals

In case the condition of the patient is very critical, it can be desirable to store the vital signs full time, comparable to the situation at the operation room. However, in case the condition of the patient is stable, it can also be chosen to store only the tendency values

or to store for example 10 minute of vital signs in the beginning, take it as a basis and compare every time interval the signs with the basis.

In case clinical decision support has a role (the post-processing of the signals), it can be chosen to store only alarm events. Therefore the equipment or the SACS should have buffer which stores every signal every second, but in that case the information can be deleted when no event occurs. In case of alarm events, the time period of the event can be stored in de SACS where it can be used for decision support by creating the knowledge base. When presented with an individual patient case, the generic knowledge in the knowledge base is applied to the specific data for that patient, using the inferencing component to reason about the specific case in light of the generic knowledge. As a result the CDSS can offer case specific advice to the clinician such as a suggested diagnosis, a suggested laboratory test or measurement to apply to find out more information, or a treatment proposal [52].

10.3 Special wishes and needs

Another special wish of the anaesthesiologist is to have a system containing information about the physical and mental state of the anaesthesiologist controlling the operation, preferably even measuring the performance of the anaesthesiologist. This 'system' is not necessarily connected to the SACS, because it must be active before the operation, but the performance measurement can be stored in the SACS together with the other signals. One way to achieve this is letting the anaesthesiologist completing a question list or completing a game testing the ability to react. In any case, a simple solution can be that before every operation the anaesthesiologist has to press a button by which he declares that his mental and physical state is fine and that he thus stands surety for the operation. If the button is not pressed, the anaesthesia equipment may not be activated. Although these kind of systems can be implemented independent of a SACS, the special wishes and needs must always be kept in mind.

11. Conclusion & Recommendations

The biggest driver for medical device connectivity within the Hospital Italiano is the raising importance of legal issues and thus being able to provide sufficient proof of good handling of the hospital staff. In order to do this the signals have to be transferred from the bedside equipment to a computer and several signals should be stored for a specific period of time in a suitable data standard. The whole system is called a Signal Archiving and Communication System (SACS) by the hospital. The single aspects of the system have been examined in the previous chapters.

The first striking conclusion is that there is no hospital wide policy regarding the storage of signals at this moment. Without clear requirements and needs from all the departments of the hospital, it is impossible to give a binding advise. Therefore it is necessary to define clear wishes and needs first. Depending on these exact requirements for the system it can be decided which of the given solutions in chapters 6, 7 and 8 will fit best. However, this doesn't exclude the fact that a specific advise for the short term can't be given.

As mentioned in chapter paragraph 4.3 not every monitor within the Hospital Italiano seems suitable for integration at this moment. Putting many effort and money in the integration of all the available monitors is not recommended. Many communication protocols only applicable for one monitor will be necessary, possible leading to uninterchangeable data formats and the reorganization of the whole physical network within the hospital. Besides that, it is conceivable that the monitor will be replaced before a signal archive is reality. For these monitors, the focus can better be put on the purchase policy of the next generation of equipment that is able to communicate with the preferred data formats. The purchasing policy will be discussed later in this chapter and the preferred data formats are discussed in paragraph 11.1.

All the mentioned solutions are able to provide the storage of signals, but many differences exist in especially price, time necessary for implementation, operability and the amount of modalities supported. An overview is given in table 7.

Criteria	Solution 1	Solution 2	Solution 3
Price	Individual datacaptor license from €20,-.	-	One year bundle licence €2.499,-.
Implement. time	-	-	few months
Data format	To be defined by HI	.png files	To be defined by HI
Operability between SACS / HIS	Yes, by HL7	Yes, by HL7	Yes
Operability between other hospitals	Yes	Yes	Depending on data type
# modalities supported	3	1	1
Guarantee /supplier service	2 days training, project management, technical sup.	-	-

Table 9 – Overview of different solutions. Prices are given in euro; 1 euro = 4,5 Argentine peso.

The boxes in table 7 without information are due to the impossibility to find the information or the unwillingness of the suppliers to provide the information.

At first sight, the preference of the hospital inclines towards the solution of CapsuleTech. However, at this moment CapsuleTech supports only three monitors within the hospital and for every department, except the operation room, it is even not clear whether storage of signals is desirable [51,53]. Therefore the CapsuleTech solution seems to be too expensive and more suitable for larger connectivity solutions than just the one at the operation room. The Ixellence software used at this moment is still a trial version which can quite easily be converted to a licensed version in order to use every available application of the software. By doing this, the functions of the storage of signals can be tried, tested and evaluated in order to obtain the required set of wishes and needs. During that period of time, more equipment within the hospital will be replaced by newer equipment and thus automatically involving more monitors into the SACS project. The new monitors are preferably originating from a worldwide supplier that is also supported by the solutions provided in chapter 6. From paragraph 10.1 it can be derived that the future will bring wireless technology and that the integration of monitors also has the tendency to become wireless. Considering the SACS, it will be a surplus value if the new monitors have the possibility of wireless connectivity.

When having clear requirements for the SACS and more extensive equipment, the decision to cooperate with one of the connectivity software suppliers can be examined once again. At this moment, CapsuleTech seems to be the most suitable solution of connecting the devices, but after contacting CapsuleTech a couple of times they seem not very willing to cooperate with a hospital in Buenos Aires. Besides CapsuleTech, Sensitron seems to be a good solution as well. They already deliver their connectivity product in Chili and good be more willing to cooperate with other countries in South America. They even provide wireless connectivity which can be a good step regarding the future.

Other important factors regarding the SACS are the communication between the SACS and the current HIS and therefore the used data format, the post processing issues and the improvement in cost savings nursing hours. Since the HIS communicates with HL7 the SACS must be able to send and receive HL7 messages as well. This can be considered as the first requirement of the system. Costs and nursing hours can only be saved and optimized when the departments provide a detailed work flow analyzes and the work flow will be redesigned according to experiences using PACS systems. An inventory of the suitable data formats is given in paragraph 11.1.

11.1 Suitable data formats

All the data formats mentioned in paragraph 4.4 are able to store the waveform core data. Therefore, other features and characteristics should be taken into account in order to select an approach that can serve as a general solution for processing waveform data [4].

The first one is the waveform domains that are covered by the standard. In the ideal situation there should be a standard that covers as many domains as possible. For example, the SCP-ECG might be good for storing ECG signals, but does not have a solution for other waveform data. Of course, all the domains have some different characteristics like recording time and frequency, but in nearly every application

waveform data consists of sequences of sampled data that can be organized in channels. In this case, DICOM, ASTM 1467, FEF, CEN, but also MFER seem more suitable.

The second important issue is the possibility of vendors to claim conformance to a standard. You want to know how it works and what features it supports before buying it. MFER doesn't provide mechanisms to achieve this, SCP-ECG and DICOM do.

The third issue is the focused on the long-term storage of signals. Therefore it is important that the standards define a communication protocol that enables the transmission of waveform data to an archive or another network. Also SCP-ECG and DICOM have protocols for such tasks and for DICOM these protocols are already in use for image archives. To use this protocol also for signals, it should only be 'activated' on a way that the SOP classes support it. Therefore DICOM seems to be a good solution, because in this case a PACS can also be used for the storage of signals. However, DICOM is quite a complex standard and for implementations starting from the beginning, for example in smaller organizations, a simpler format might be more appropriate. This can, however, introduce other complications for the future regarding the interoperability with other systems.

Other issues of interest are compression ratios and the way annotations can be made. Some standards allow a compression of the core waveform data which can be of importance for the necessary storage capacities. SCP-ECG provides can achieve compression ratios up to 20:1. DICOM offers the 'deflated transfer syntax' that can be used to apply a lossless ZIP compression to all data. All the standards specify mechanisms to annotate the waveform data, but SCP-ECG offers the most.

Discussion

The original assignment proposal was formulated to give a recommendation about the integration of vital signs into a SACS. This proposal could be interpreted in many ways and the focus can be put on many aspects of the integration process. It is decided to make the focus broad and take all the aspects into account which can be found out on forehand. I think this was a good decision, because no information is available in the hospital regarding information about dataformats, existing databases, vital signs and pre- and postprocessing issues. This information could be found in scientific literature without any trouble. This was in contrast with the information about the software suppliers like CapsuleTech. It took many efforts to obtain a reaction with all the information asked for. Due to the help of Dr. Val Jones they finally gave a reaction, but it seemed impossible to get detailed information about the software structure and prices. Whether this is due to the fact that they knew they were communicating with the Hospital Italiano in Buenos Aires is still unclear, but it could be a reason. Maybe they are less interested in working with a hospital in Argentina and therefore serious interest in the program should be shown the next the of contacting CapsuleTech.

Additional research is necessary to look to the exact way of communication between the current HIS and the future SACS; how can the SACS be implemented in the existing HIS? Therefore it is also necessary to make a more exact calculation about the required data capacity than is given in paragraph 9.4 This shows the ranges of the capacity, but huge differences in price exist between a system containing a few Gb or a few Tb. Besides that, additional research can also be provided for the special wishes of the anaesthesiologist regarding the system which is able to measure his performance. This can partly be done regardless the SACS, but a clear approach is necessary.

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Appendix 1:

The IntelliVue Clinical Network

